

Deliverable D-JRP26-WP2.1

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: VISAVET-UCM
Contributing partners: PIWET, WBVR, APHA,
ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	<i>Salmonella</i> controls at the primary production level - Comparative analysis of <i>Salmonella</i> controls and management measures in laying hen farms at MSs level		
WP and Task	D-JRP26-WP2.1		
Leader	VISAVET-UCM		
Other contributors	PIWET, WBVR, APHA, ANSES		
Due month of the deliverable	43		
Actual finalization month	47		
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other	international	stakeholder
	(s):.....		
	Social Media:		
	Other recipient(s):		

Salmonella controls at the primary production level

Comparative analysis of *Salmonella* controls and management measures in laying hen farms at Member State level - Surveys

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Introduction

A survey on different aspects of the *Salmonella* National Control Programs (SNCPs) in laying hens has been sent to all partners in Work Package 2 of the ADONIS project - One Health European Joint Program (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-adonis/>). It has been completed with the advice of the official veterinary services from their countries when needed. The survey aimed to identify similarities and differences in the implementation of SNCPs at Member States (MSs) level in order to help understand the evolution in the prevalence of *Salmonella* infection in laying hens over the last decade.

The contact person ultimately facilitating the data for each country is as follows:

- Spain. Data source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food / Animal Health Department (MAPA). Contact person: Soledad Collado , Cristina Caballero (MAPA), Clara Samper-Cativiela and Julio Álvarez (Veterinary Health Surveillance Centre, VISAVET)
- Poland. Data source: General Veterinary Inspectorate, Animal Health and Welfare Office. Contact persons: Magdalena Gawędzka (General Veterinary Inspectorate, GVI), Dariusz Wasyl and Jowita Niczyporuk (PIWET)
- The Netherlands. Data source: Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority, Dutch Poultry Farmers Association (AVINED) and Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (WBVR). Contact persons: Miriam Koene and Henk Wisselink (WBVR)
- The United Kingdom (UK). Data source: Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra). Contact person: Kate Newton, Andrew Frost and Shaun Cawthraw (Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)).
- France. Data source: French Ministry of Agriculture. Contact person: Adeline Huneau-Salaün and Marianne Chemaly (*Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire, ANSES*)

Keypoints

- The **population** size of **laying hens** in the countries assessed varied greatly (between ~37 to and ~86 million animals/ 2.135 and 5.651 flocks), showing an upward trend over the 2013-2019 period in some countries.
- Cage-based **systems** were still the predominant production type in four of the five countries, although their relative importance has decreased steadily in the last decade as they are replaced by cage-free systems.
- **Small holdings for self-consumption** are never included in the scope of the SNCPs, although how these small holdings, with eggs not entering the market, are defined depends on the country.
- Auto-control checks varied from official controls in:
 - Frequency: Defined vs. throughout the year and cycles of animal production
 - Sampler: Food Borne Operators (FBO) vs. Competent Authorities (CA) - veterinaries.
 - Flock sampled (any flock vs. the oldest)
 - Sample matrix
 - Laboratories involved in the analysis
- Auto-control checks and official controls did not vary in the laboratory methods followed and measures implemented in case of *Salmonella* detection
- Similar protocols for both auto-control checks and official controls were implemented in all countries (type and number of samples, sampling frequency) in each animal category (age range).
- Target serovars were the same (*S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*) in every country except in France, where additional serovars are considered at earlier production stages (*S. Kentucky*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Virchow* and *S. Hadar* at one-day-old chicks and *S. Kentucky* also at 4 weeks old).
- Similar measures (immobilisation, eggs delivered to treatment plants and commercialised as egg products) were implemented in all countries in cases of positive target *Salmonella* results.
- Financial compensation in cases of positive flocks (cost derived from immobilisation and slaughter) is only provided in some countries.
- Biosecurity measures lie on FBO, but different Cleaning & Disinfection (C&D) guidelines are followed.
- Vaccination is not compulsory (except in Spain), but high vaccination coverage against *S. Enteritidis* is reckon in some of the surveyed countries. No accurate data is available for France.
- Data availability on auto-control checks and official controls in each country varied. Data on vaccination status is not available or is not fully reliable.
- Slight variations in the implementation of SNCPs between countries have been found, which could have a limited, unquantified effect on their performance.

Section 1. Population and scope of the program

1. Population at flock and animal level

The number of laying hens varied in the five countries included in the survey (Table 1), with larger populations in France and Poland (>70 million animals) compared to Spain (45-68 million) and the Netherlands (<50 million), while the UK had the fewest number of birds (<42 million). The number of flocks was also higher in France (close to or above 5000) followed by the UK (ranging between 4000-5000), Poland and Spain (between 2000-3000) and the Netherlands (<1500 farms) (Table 1). Flock numbers increased steadily over the 2013-2019 study period for France, the UK and Spain, while remaining stable in Poland and decreasing in the Netherlands (Table 1). The ratio between the number of animals and the number of flocks indicates variation in mean size of flocks, with the largest found in Poland and the smallest in the UK.

Table 1. Population of laying hens (animals = millions, flocks = thousand) per year and country.

		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
ES	Animal	52.253 k	45.245 k	-	65.166 k	63.351 k	67.772 k	69.875 k	70.256 k
	Flocks	2.135	2.374	-	2.617	2.793	2.943	3.076	3.137
PL	Animal	74.339 k	80.486 k	76.374 k	75.753 k	71.381 k	80.905 k	-	-
	Flocks	3.072	3.024	2.887	2.857	2.803	2.827	2.252	-
NL	Animal	44.815 k	46.570 k	47.684 k	46.212 k	46.441 k	47.302 k	44.319 k	43.166 k
	Farms*	1.219	1.170	1.124	1.017	993	891	867	856
UK	Animal	35.840 k	37.145 k	36.998 k	38.057 k	39,500	39.851 k	41.534 k	37.266k
	Flocks	3.991	3.940	4.056	4.286	4.428	4.677	4.614	4.578
FR	Animal	79.817 k	76.093 k	-	-	-	-	86.288 k	-
	Flocks	4.974	4.928	5.243	5.362	5.433	5.651	6.400	-

2. Production system

Laying hens are kept in different systems, among which loose housing systems (non-cages) have increasing importance. Nevertheless, the predominant production system was variable depending on the country (Table2, Figure 1): cage was still the primary production type in Spain, Poland, and France, although with very different percentages (82, 61 and 47% respectively). In the UK, free range was the most common production system (55%), while for the Netherlands, it was barn (60.2%).

Table 2. Proportion of flocks maintained in different production systems (data shown corresponds to 2018 for ES, PL, NL, UK and 2020 for FR)

	ES	PL	NL	UK	FR
Free range	7%	13%	19,3%	55%	23%*
Cage***	82%	61%	13,5%	40%	47%
Barn	10%**	23%	60%**	2%	12%
Ecologic/Organic	1%	3%	7%	3%	18%

* label rouge and plein air ** also including aviaries *** enriched cages

Figure 3. Production system per country (data shown corresponds to 2018 for ES, PL, NL, UK and 2020 for FR).

A steady decrease in the percentage of hens kept in cages was reported for all countries except Poland, where no significant changes were reported in recent years. In the Netherlands, it decreased from 45% in 2008 to 14% in 2018, leading to a steady increase in alternative production systems (barn, ecologic and free range). A decreasing trend in cage-based production has also been observed in Spain since 2008, with a corresponding increase in alternative production systems, which grew from 3.5% in 2007 to 17.7% in 2018. This change is also evident in the UK, where free range has become more common while enriched cage and organic production have remained similar and barn production has decreased. In France, the number of hens in cages has decreased since 2015, with an increase in the number of hens in barns and aviaries. Free-ranged and organic hens have also increased in this period.

3. Scope of the program

All production systems described above are included by the respective SNCPs in place in each country according to the European Regulation (EC) No 1177/2006 implementing Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 (first applied in 2008 although other regulations were already in place in certain countries before this date). However, the scope of the program can have certain modifications depending on the country (for example, in France, S. Kentucky was added as a target of the SNCPs in some stages of laying hen production and in other poultry species in 2015).

In general terms, SNCs do not apply to small farms devoted to the direct supply of small quantities to traditional markets and private domestic use/self-consumption (eggs not entering the market). However, different definitions may be used in each country to entitle such self-consumption small holdings, so that in Spain, each region set the limit in terms of egg/animals, in Poland the program does not apply to farms with less than 2.450 eggs a week, in the UK if the premises have fewer than 350 hens and in France and the Netherlands to flocks under 250 laying hens.

Section 2. Auto-control checks performed by Food Business Operators (FBO)

Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 stipulates a minimum sampling requirement for auto-control checks by FBO, although the type and number of samples collected and the sampling frequency varied slightly between countries (Table 3a, 3b). There were notable differences found in France, where serotypes other than *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* are also considered in pullets (Table 3b). In general, samples are collected on arrival at the farm (one-day-old chicks), within the two weeks before the start of the laying period and every fifteen weeks during the production period (adult hens).

Sample types/matrix from day-old chick deliveries included faeces from box liners, inlay sheets from boxes, and liver, yolk, and meconium of dead chicks. The number of individual samples collected varied depending on the matrix, although these are commonly pooled into one sample at processing (Table 3a, 3b)

Samples collected two weeks before laying included faeces (around 150 g) and fabric boot swabs. In general, swabs are preferred in free-range, barn, and organic facilities (where faecal material is cleared away), and faeces are more commonly collected in cage systems. Similar samples can be collected during the production period, which generally starts when animals are 22-26 weeks old, although sampling belts and scrapers are also options in Spain and the UK.

Sampling is the responsibility of the stakeholder/ FBO, although other staff (including the farmer, company/farm veterinary, or laboratory personnel) may be involved in the process. Costs incurred (intervention, sampling material, and laboratory analysis) are covered by the FBO. Samples must be shipped to and processed in authorised laboratories, including Official Regional laboratories and private laboratories approved by the appropriate competent regional or national (depending on the country) authority. These laboratories must work under accreditation, with tests for *Salmonella* detection in all matrices accredited under ISO/IEC 17025 (“Testing Calibration Laboratories”) and apply quality assurance systems for this standard. In all countries surveyed, laboratories involved in testing FBO auto-control checks are inspected routinely by independent auditors and participate in proficiency test exercises to ensure their reliability.

All countries work to the same laboratory test protocols. Isolation of *Salmonella* follows ISO 6579-1:2017 “Microbiology of the food chain-Horizontal method for the detection

enumeration and serotyping of *Salmonella*- Part 1: Detection of *Salmonella* spp” using a semi-solid medium (Modified Semi-Solid Rappaport-Vassiliadis -MSRV- Agar) as the selective enrichment medium. Serotyping of cultured isolates follows the White-Kaufmann-Le Minor schema. In Spain, France and the Netherlands, standardized or alternative methods can be used if they have been validated in accordance with internationally recognised rules (ISO 16140-2) and offer equivalent results to those obtained by the relevant reference method.

1. Measures and financial compensation

Where a positive sample is detected in a flock, the measures taken (mandatory slaughter, restriction of movements) differ slightly depending on the country. In France, the Netherlands and Poland the stakeholder must notify the Directorate Veterinary Officer (DVO), and ensure that sale products (eggs) are not moved to or from the premises and no movements of live birds of that flock take place (no more animals can be introduced). In the UK and Spain, the laboratory identifying *Salmonella* must notify the CA of their findings and the stakeholder must restrict the movement of eggs.

An official confirmatory sampling conducted by CA can follow in certain situations and on a case-by-case basis, for example when a reasonable suspicion of improper sampling (not according to Regulation (EU) 517/2011) exists. All countries have been advised not to do official confirmatory sampling as a routine.

In every country, eggs from positive flocks (regulated *Salmonella* zoonotic serotypes, Community legislation) may be heat-treated before human consumption. These are considered class B eggs. Eggs produced by infected flocks cannot reach egg packing centres and are delivered directly to a specific plant for either heat treatment or destruction.

The Government pays no compensation for animals slaughtered in Poland and the UK. However, farmers usually purchase additional insurances (e.g. the UK and Spain). In Spain a national compensation exists and some regional governments can apply extra compensations in specific cases. In the Netherlands, compensation for the cost of bacteriological examinations of the 300 chickens is paid by the Dutch Animal Health Fund (formed by the farmers, Government, and the European Union (EU)). In France, financial support from Veterinary authorities is provided to farms that voluntarily engage in the national program for *Salmonella* prevention called “Charte Sanitaire” (two-thirds of

French farms adhered in 2019). Epidemiological surveys are always conducted in Poland, Spain, the UK, and France when flocks are positive for target serovars.

Table 3a. Number and type of samples collected per country and hen categories (Spain, Poland, the Netherlands and the UK).

Hen categories	ES	PL	NL	UK
One-day-old chicks	Samples of faeces from lining boxes (10 gathered in 1 sample), liver, the yolk of 60 dead chicks (1 sample) or 250 chicks meconium (1 sample) from transport containers.	Samples of faeces from lining boxes, liver, liver, dead chicks or meconium (1 sample) from transport containers.	Samples of faeces from lining boxes (forty), liver, dead chicks or meconium from transport containers.	Samples of faeces from lining boxes (up to 10 boxes, one box for every 500 chicks), the carcasses dead chicks (up to 60 carcasses from each hatchery) from transport containers.
2 weeks before laying phase	Cage: One sample (min. 1g) of faeces per poultry house from at least 10 different points from the local (proportional to the number of animals) Free-range, barn, organic: two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house.	Cage: Two samples of 150g faeces per poultry house. Free-range, barn, organic: two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house. Alternatively: one pair of boot swabs plus one pair fabric swabs or 4 fabric swabs.	Cage: Two samples of 150g faeces per poultry house. Free-range, barn, organic: two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house.	Cage: Two samples of 150g faeces per poultry house. Free-range, barn, organic: two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house.
Adult hens (every 15 wk. during production period, with the first time generally at 24 wk. +/- 2 and until 2-3 weeks before slaughter)	Cage: Two samples of 150g faeces per poultry house (from belts or scrapers in the house after running the manure removal system) Barn, free-range, organic: Two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house. Alternatively in step cage houses with not enough faeces in scrapers four moistened fabric swabs (min. surface 900cm ²).	Cage: Two samples of 150g faeces per poultry house Barn, free-range, organic: Two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house. Alternatively: one pair of boot swabs plus one pair fabric swabs or 4 fabric swabs.	Cage: Two samples of 150g faeces per poultry house Barn, free-range, organic: Two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house.	Cage: Two samples of 150g faeces per poultry house Caged houses where enough faeces do not accumulate on scrapers or belt cleaners at the discharge end of belts, 4 or more moistened fabric swabs (at least 900cm ² per swab) can be used. Barn, free-range, organic: Two pairs of boot swabs per poultry house. Alternatively in cages houses where the faecal material is removed: one pair of boot swabs plus at least 2 moistened fabric swabs.
Serotypes	SE, ST	SE, ST	SE, ST	SE, ST

Table 3b. Number and type of samples collected and determined serotypes per hen categories (ages) in France.

Age		Samples	Serotype
One-day-old (pullets)	Barn and cage	5 box liners (+ 5 box liners stored for 8 weeks at the lab)	SE ST SH SI SV SK
4-week-old (pullets)	Barn	2 pairs of boot swabs + 2 swabs (dust etc.)	SE ST SK
	Cage	2 swabs on dropping belts + 1 swab on 20 cages (floor of the cage) + 1 dust swab	
Within 2 weeks before transfer (pullets)	Barn	2 pairs of boot swabs + 2 swabs (dust etc.)	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.
	Cage	2 swabs on dropping belts + 1 swab on 20 cages (floor of the cage) + 1 dust swab	
Within 4 weeks after transfer (<25 wk.) In case of 2nd laying cycle (after moulting): 1 week of the laying period	Barn	2 pair of boot swabs + 1 swab (dust...) from 1000 to 20000 hens OR 2 swabs (dust...) from 20001 to 50000 OR 3 swabs (dust...) from 50001 to 80000 OR 4 swabs (dust...) > 80000 + 500 g feed (> 80000 hens*)	SE ST
	Cage	2*150 g droppings + 1 swab (dust...) from 1000 to 20000 hens OR 2 swabs (dust...) from 20001 to 50000 OR 3 swabs (dust...) from 50001 to 80000 OR 4 swabs (dust...) > 80000 + 500 g feed (> 80000 hens*)	
Every 15 weeks after the first control (+/- 2 wk.)	Barn	2 pair of boot swabs + 1 swab (dust...) from 1000 to 20000 hens OR 2 swabs (dust...) from 20001 to 50000 OR 3 swabs (dust...) from 50001 to 80000 OR 4 swabs (dust...) > 80000 + 500 g feed (> 80000 hens*)	
	Cage	2*150 g droppings + 1 swab (dust...) from 1000 to 20000 hens OR 2 swabs (dust...) from 20001 to 50000 OR 3 swabs (dust...) from 50001 to 80000 OR 4 swabs (dust...) > 80000 + 500 g feed (> 80000 hens*)	
Within 6 weeks before slaughter	Barn	2 pair of boot swabs + 1 swab (dust...) from 1000 to 20000 hens OR 2 swabs (dust...) from 20001 to 50000 OR 3 swabs (dust...) from 50001 to 80000 OR 4 swabs (dust...) > 80000 + 500 g feed (> 80000 hens*)	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Within 10 weeks before slaughter	Cage	2*150 g droppings + 1 swab (dust...) from 1000 to 20000 hens OR 2 swabs (dust...) from 20001 to 50000 OR 3 swabs (dust...) from 50001 to 80000 OR 4 swabs (dust...) > 80000 + 500 g feed (> 80000 hens)	

Section 3. Official control performed by Competent Authorities (CA)

In general terms, there are no major differences between official controls and auto-control checks (Section 2). However, every country conducts official controls throughout the year, unlike auto-controls that follow specific time protocols (following laying hen lifetime). In addition, authorised personnel, generally veterinary authorities, oversee these official samplings.

As a general rule, official controls are performed once per year from one flock on every holding with >1,000 birds during period of production, at the age of 24 +/- 2 weeks in laying flocks housed in buildings where the relevant *Salmonella* was detected in the preceding flock. Controls are also performed on all flocks on the holding when *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* including monophasic variant are detected in any flocks on a holding, and when there is an epidemiological link to a case of human disease in a foodborne outbreak or in cases where the competent authority considers it appropriate.

Thus, there are some specific, minor differences between official controls and auto-control checks. Large farms (>1000 adult hens) are more commonly chosen for official control, and CA generally prioritise those farms that had positive flocks in previous official and auto-control samplings. In addition, the oldest flock in the farm is commonly the one selected, although in the UK officials select random flocks.

The sample scheme is similar to that followed in auto-controls checks (dropping belt swabs for cage systems and boot swabs for barn, free-range and organic systems) (Table 3a, 3b). In some countries further samples may be taken to ensure they are representative of larger flocks. In some countries, such as Spain, the CA may decide to replace one sample of faeces or boot swabs with a sample of dust from various points (100 g or using a 900 cm² of moistened fabric swabs). In others, such as the UK, this decision can vary depending on the region (e.g. dust is not collected as part of routine annual official sampling in Northern Ireland).

1. Measures and financial compensation

Where positive flocks are detected during official controls, measures implemented are the same as in auto-control checks. (Section 2). Financial compensation schemes are also the same as those described for auto-control checks (Section 2)

Section 4. Biosecurity measures

In every country, biosecurity surveys (checking biosecurity status and measures implemented at the farms) are conducted when Official Control samples are collected, and biosecurity measures are commonly verified once a year (exceptions). Specifically, in the Netherlands, biosecurity measures are inspected at the holding by the private quality system “Integrale Keten Beheersing” (IKB), and in France, farms are also inspected by local veterinary authorities every three years. In Poland, inspections are carried by veterinarians, and these take place mainly following the occurrence of a poultry disease outbreak (e.g., avian influenza). In the UK, biosecurity on each laying farm is assessed at least once a year, and advice may also be given regarding remedial measures and flock turnaround times following additional visits conducted if a regulated serotype has been identified on a specific site. In Spain, biosecurity surveys follow the NCPs instructions and some regional authorities have developed guidance about how to complete the pattern on order to unify criteria

1. Cleaning and disinfection (C&D)

In every country, verification of the C&D process is performed according to its own SNCPs pattern guidance. The de-population C&D process is conducted in farms once the flocks have been slaughtered. This process includes an efficient and complete cleaning (including complete removal of litter and droppings) and subsequent disinfection, disinsection and rodent extermination.

Following the culling of birds in infected flocks, and after an adequate time has elapsed after disinfection, environmental samples will be taken to verify the effectiveness of the cleaning and disinfection work and confirm the absence of *Salmonella* spp. in the environment. Barns where positive flocks were located are sampled after the C&D (several environmental swabs collected in predefined sites) and tested according to ISO 6579-1:2017-04 to confirm the effectiveness of the process. In the Netherlands this is conducted by IKB, in the UK and Spain sampling is the stakeholder responsibility (payment and personnel). In the event of persistent carry over of infection into subsequent flocks, official intervention measures include the option for official enhanced environment sampling (e.g. the UK and Spain).

2. Vaccines

Vaccination is not mandatory nowadays in any country (it was previously) except for Spain, where all laying hens will undergo mandatory vaccination against *S. Enteritidis* during the growing phase (some farms with negative tests and adequate biosecurity measures may be exempt). However, even if no obligation exists in the other countries, they all report a high vaccination coverage (lack of consistent data for France), so that at commercial scale almost all flocks are vaccinated against *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium*. (e.g. 1028/1174 flocks in the Netherlands in 2019).

The list of licensed, live (attenuated) and inactivated *Salmonella* vaccines varies slightly per country (Table 4). Live vaccines are generally administered via the drinking water, and inactivated vaccines via the intramuscular route. Live vaccine strains must be

distinguishable from field strains. Until 2020 every country restricted the use of live vaccines (attenuated) during laying phase, but in Spain the use of PRIMUM SALMONELLA E has recently been authorised for administration at 44 weeks of age. In France, live attenuated vaccines are allowed under restrictive conditions but are very rarely used.

The costs of vaccination are generally the responsibility of stakeholders. However, some regional, veterinary public services finance the cost of vaccination partially or even totally. Information on vaccination is poorly reported by the farmers (and poorly recorded in the national database by local veterinary authorities) in every country. Due to its mandatory nature, Spain has a more complete data collection concerning vaccination, whilst in France the poultry sector has recently developed a data recording scheme (Table 5).

Table 4 . List of authorised vaccines per country.

Type	Vaccine name	Serotypes / Active Substance	Company / Manufacturer	Administration route	Dosage schedule	Duration of immunity to (according manufacturer)	Allowed at laying phase	Country	Link
Inactivated	AVIASAN SECURE	SE (PT4) ST (DT 104)	HIPRA, S.A.	INTRAMUSCULAR	2 dosis: 10 weeks 17 weeks	45-50 weeks	No	ES	https://www.hipra.com/portal/es/hipra/animalhealth/products/detail/avisan-secure
	GALLIMUNE SE+ST	SE (PT4) ST(DT104) Formalin	BOEHRINGER INGELHEIM ANIMAL HEALTH S.A.U	INTRAMUSCULAR	2 dosis: 6 weeks 16 weeks	4 weeks after vaccination 52 weeks for SE 61 weeks for ST	No, Last vaccination until two weeks for the laying phase	ES, PL, NL, UK*,FR	https://5mPublishing.siv.com/es/boehringer/Gallimune_Se+St.pdf
	NOBILIS SALENVAC T	SE (PT4) ST (ST104) Formalin	MERCK SHARP & DOHME ANIMAL HEALTH, S.L	INTRAMUSCULAR	2 dosis: 12 weeks 16 weeks	56 – 60 weeks	No,	ES, PL, NL, UK*,FR	https://www.msd-animal-health-h
	NOBILIS SALENVAC ETC	SE (PT4) ST (ST104) SI (S1169)	MERCK SHARP & DOHME ANIMAL HEALTH, S.L	INTRAMUSCULAR	2 dosis: 12 weeks 16 weeks	After 7 months loss activity	No	ES, PL, NL, UK*, FR	https://www.safe-poultry.com/nobilis-salenvac-etc.aspx
	NOBILIS SALENVAC	SE(PT4)	MERCK SHARP & DOHME ANIMAL HEALTH, S.L	INTRAMUSCULAR	2 dosis: 12 weeks 16 weeks		No	UK*	https://www.safe-poultry.com/NobilisSalenvac_FAQ.aspx
	Hipratifus-AV2	SE (PT4) ST (DT 104)	HIPRA, S.A.	INTRAMUSCULAR	2 dosis: 12 weeks 18 weeks		No	PL	https://www.google.com/search?q=HIPRATIFUS+AV2&rlz=1C1CHBD_esES912ES912&oeq=HIPRATIFUS+AV2&aqs=chrome..69j57j69j60j3.5020j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8#
	S.E.T. -VAC	SE ST	THLALA KOLO LTD	INTRAMUSCULAR	2 dosis		No	PL	https://thialakolo.com/product/set-vac-fowl-typhoid-vaccine/
Attenuated (live)	AVIPRO SALMONELLA DUO	SE (SM24/RIF12/SSQ) ST(NAL2/RIF9/RTT)	ELANCO GMBH	DRINKING WATER	3 dosis: 1 st day 6-8 weeks 16 weeks	Starts 15 days after 46 weeks-322 days(ST) 52 weeks - 364 days (SE) *from the time of the last vaccination	No Last vaccination at least 3 weeks before onset of lay	ES, PL, NL, UK*, FR	https://www.elanco.com.ar/productos/avicultura/salmonelladu
	AVIPRO SALMONELLA VAC E	SE (SM24/RIF12/SSQ)	ELANCO GMBH	DRINKING WATER	3 dosis: 1 st day 6-8 weeks 16 weeks	Starts 14 days after 1st dosis 52 weeks - 364 days	No Last vaccination at least 3 weeks before onset of lay	ES, PL, NL, UK*, FR	https://www.elanco.com.ar/productos/avicultura/salmonelladu
	AVIPRO SALMONELLA VAC T	ST	ELANCO GMBH	DRINKING WATER	3 dosis: 1 st day 6-8 weeks 16 weeks	Starts 15 after 50 weeks - 322 days	No	ES, PL, NL, UK*	https://www.elanco.com.ar/productos/avicultura/salmonelladu
	SALMOVAC 440	SE (441/014)	IDT BIOLOGIKA GMBH	DRINKING WATER	3 dosis: 1st day 6 weeks 13 weeks	Starts 6 days after 60 weeks ST 63 weeks SE	No	ES, PL, NL, UK*	https://www.ceva.es/Especies-y-Productos/Lista-de-productos/SALMOVAC-440
	PRIMUM SALMONELLA E	SE (CAL 10 SM+ /RIF +/SSQ-)	CALIER, S.A.	DRINKING WATER	3/4 dosis: 1st day 6-8 weeks 15-20 weeks *55 weeks	Starts at 14 days 80 weeks after 3 rd vaccination 40 weeks after 4 th vaccination	Yes. Allowed a 4 th dosis during laying phase at 44 th weeks	ES	https://www.calier.com/espana/es-es/vademecum/primum-salmonella-e
	NOBILIS SE LIVE	SE (CAL 10 SM+ /RIF +/SSQ-)	MERCK SHARP & DOHME ANIMAL HEALTH, S.L	DRINKING WATER	3 dosis: 1 st day 7-8 weeks 18-20 weeks	Starts 14 days after the 1 st 60 weeks	No, Last vaccination at least three weeks before onset of lay	PL, NL	https://www.vmd.defra.gov.uk/productinformationdatabase/files/SPC_Documents/SPC_1411249.PDF
	NOBILIS SG 9R	SG 9R SE	MERCK SHARP & DOHME ANIMAL HEALTH, S.L	DRINKING WATER			No	PL	https://www.msd-salud-animal.com.ar/productos/nobilis-sg-9r/
	SG-VAC LIVE	SG		DRINKING WATER			No	PL	?

*UK: Note that post Brexit veterinary drugs are licensed for use in Northern Ireland and separately for use in Great Britain.

Available data

Table 5. Data availability per country on FBO & CA sampling recordings and vaccination status of the flocks.

	ES	PL	NL	UK	FR
FBO & CA	Yes, Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food. Animal Health Department.	No, maybe protocols from facilities inspection maybe gathered from GVI.	Yes, KIPnet. Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO) and the competent authority (NVWA).	Yes, Government (APHA-FSA). Including WGS sequence.	Yes, Anses – French Ministry of Agriculture.
Vaccination	Yes (but not completely reliable), Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food: Animal Health Department.	Yes, recorded in cover letters.	Yes, but vaccination is not registered in a central official database.	No.	No. But a new database has been developed by the egg sector

Discussion

In 2008 the European Community adopted regulations to reduce and control *Salmonella* infection in laying hens and eggs across the EU, including a trade ban on eggs from flocks infected by the regulated (target) *Salmonella* serovars set out in legislation. These regulations initially aimed for an annual minimum reduction of 10-40% in the number of positive flocks, with the ultimate target of 2% or less of flocks being positive for *Salmonella*. After thirteen years, the high numbers of *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* (main target serovars) positive layer flocks have been reduced significantly, and the objective of reaching less than 2% positivity has been achieved in almost every country. In the last few years, the levels have reached a plateau. This stabilization could be due to a variety of factors, and this survey was undertaken in order to detect differences that could lie behind the transposition of the regulation at MSs level. The answers revealed only slight differences between countries regarding the scope and application of these SNCPs. This was to be expected, since all countries work under the named European Regulation (EC) No 1177/2006. and 517/2011 However, some differences have been identified.

Although the scope of the program is the same in all countries, the populations of laying hens and the relative importance of the different production systems varies between countries. Similarly, the definition of small holdings, which are not included in the scope of the SNCPs in any country, is variable and can be based on size (number of animals) or production (number of eggs) parameters. These differences, and others related to poultry production holdings (e.g. facilities sizes), could be a factor affecting how control measures are applied and, therefore, in the number of *Salmonella* positive samples.

Similar protocols regarding the type and number of samples, the sampling frequency for the different age animal categories and target serotypes were applied for both auto-control checks and official controls in these countries. However, animal classification and target serotype definition varied in some countries (France), and sample types seem to be more variable. In addition, public mechanisms of financial compensation (if needed) exist in some countries such as the Netherlands (for the costs of bacteriological examination of the chickens) and in France (in case of animal immobilization), while the use of private insurance was more common in others (e.g. the UK). In Spain a public-private financial system is followed, with some fees covered by the Government.

With regards to biosecurity measures, a responsibility that lies with the owners/farmers, each country follows its own specific guidelines (not specified in the surveys). In terms of vaccination, each country has its own list of allowed vaccines and its exceptions. Vaccination was initially mandatory in an effort to reduce the national prevalences to 10% or less, but currently, vaccination is only mandatory in Spain (even though the incidence is below this number). In addition, live vaccination is generally forbidden during the laying phase, which can leave hens unprotected in the late stages of production. However, a live *S. Enteritidis* vaccine has recently been licensed in Spain for in-lay administration. Generally, a lack of information regarding the vaccination status of production flocks has been identified in all countries, although some improvement in recent years has been noted.

In summary, the populations included in the SNCs in each country varied mainly in terms of numbers and production types, but the measures implemented were broadly similar. Still, certain variations in the way measures are implemented were identified, and these could have a limited yet unquantified effect on their performance.

Abbreviations and definitions

ADONIS. Assessing Determinants of the non decreasing Incidence of Salmonella
APHA. Animal and Plant Health Agency (UK)
AVINED. Dutch Poultry Farmers Association (NL)
CA. Competent Authorities
C&D. Cleaning and disinfection
COKZ. The Netherlands Controlling Authority for Dairy and Eggs (*Controle Orgaan Kwaliteits Zaken*)
CVO. Chief Veterinary Officer (may also be the Regional Competent authority)
DVO. Directorate Veterinary Officer
ES. Spain
FBO. Food Business Operators
FR. France
GVI. General Veterinary Inspectorate (PL)
GVO. Government Veterinary Officer
IKB. Private quality control system from NL (*Integrale Keten Beheersing*)
ISO. International Organization for Standardization
PHA-FSA: Public Health Agency- Food Safety Agency (UK)
PIWET. National Veterinary Research Institute, Pulawy (PL)
PL. Poland
PT. Phage type
NCPs. National Control Programs
NL. the Netherlands
MAPA. Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ES)
MSRV. Modified Semi-Solid Rappaport-Vassiliadis
RVO. Regional Veterinary Officer
SG. *Salmonella* Gallinarum
SH. *Salmonella* Hadar
SK. *Salmonella* Kentucky
SNCPs. *Salmonella* National Control Programs
SE. *Salmonella* Enteritidis
ST. *Salmonella* Typhimurium
SV. *Salmonella* Virchow
UK. United Kingdom
VISAVET- UCM. Veterinary Health Surveillance Centre- Universidad Complutense de Madrid
WBVR. Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
wk/s. - weeks

Barn systems: hens are kept in houses that might have multiple tiers (aviaries) with nest boxes and perches. The floor is covered with litter material. There is a maximum of 9 hens per m² usable area.

Cages systems: hens are kept in cages with 750 cm² space per hen, and these are equipped with a perch, nest, scratching area, and nail shortener.

Free range systems: hens are kept inside identical to barn systems, but access to a pasture of 4 m² per hen is provided.

Organic systems: are a specific form of free range systems, hens are kept according to the requirements of organic production (EC, 2008). Inside no more than 6 non beak-trimmed hens per m² usable area are kept, and the hens have access to a pasture like free range hens. Besides, the hens receive feed according to organic standards. The feed ingredients are grown without synthetic fertilizers, no free amino acids are added to the feed and genetic modified soya is not used either.

Label rouge: A specific kind of free range system performed in France.

Annex I. Delivered Survey

Assessing Determinants of the non-decreasing incidence of Salmonella
ADONIS

WP2

Salmonella controls at the primary production level

Survey for comparative analysis of Salmonella controls and management measures at MSs level

The aim of this survey is to gather information about Salmonella control and management programs in countries involved in the ADONIS project of the One Health European Joint Program (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-adonis/>). This survey should be filled in by somebody with a good knowledge of Salmonella National Control Plans and how they have been implemented in the last decade. The current aim of the survey is control of Salmonella in laying hen (*Gallus gallus*) production.

Additional sources of information at the EU level that can be helpful when filling in the survey can be found at:

- https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_borne_diseases/salmonella_en
- https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/apro_ec_egghen_ismseg.htm#meta_update_1574416577016
- https://ec.europa.eu/food/funding/animal-health/national-veterinary-programmes_en.

Country:

Name:

Affiliation:

Section 1. Population and scope of the program

1. What is the total population of laying hen (included in the NCP) in your country? If possible, provide data for the last six years:

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Animal						
Flocks						

2. What is the (approximate) proportion of the total laying hen population under the following production conditions?

- Free-range:
- Cage:
- Barn (including aviaries)
- Organic

3. Has the predominant type(s) of laying hen production system(s) changed significantly in the last decade? If so, how?

4. What kind of laying hen production system are covered by the NCP in Official Control?
 - Free-range
 - Cage
 - Barn (including aviaries)
 - Organic

5. Are there specific farm types not covered by the NCP? (i.e., flocks with less than 250 laying hen)

6. When was the programme (SNCP) first implemented in the country? (year)

Section 2. Auto-control checks performed by Food Business Operators (FBO)

7. What type of samples are collected for auto-control checks in each of the production stages?

Hen categories (add others if appropriate)	Type of sampling
1 day old chicks	
2 weeks before laying	
Adult hens (each 15 weeks)	

8. Who perform auto-control checks? Who pays? [e.g. authorised private vets perform the sampling and are paid by the regional veterinary services (state budget); sampling equipment is provided by the private laboratory testing the samples which includes the price in the invoice which is paid by the local state veterinary services (state budget)]

9. Who performs the laboratory tests for the auto-control checks? Who pays? [e.g. regional public laboratories perform the testing of official samples and costs related to this testing are entirely paid by the state budget]

10. What kind of laboratories are involved in auto-control checks? (check all applicable)
 - Official laboratory
 - Authorised laboratory
 - Others (specify):

11. Are laboratory tests conducted according to specific protocols/methods? If so, please specify (e.g., ISO 6579, MicroSEQ, IQ- Check)

12. In case of positive flocks in auto-control checks, what measures are (typically) conducted?
13. Is there any compensation in case of taking measures after positive results in auto-control checks? Who pays in case of compensation? [e.g. compensation is paid by the central level of the state veterinary services, or compensation is paid by an insurance fund fed by compulsory farmers contribution]
14. Are epidemiological surveys carried out when auto-control checks are conducted? Is it possible to access the data?
- Yes, always
 - Yes when/if positive results are obtained
 - No
 - Other (specify):
15. Are facilities inspected at the same time auto-control checks are being conducted? Is there any information about the status of the buildings, the presence of biosecurity measures or the presence of rodents/other animals?
16. Is the size of the flock and poultry age recorded in auto-control checks?
- Yes
 - No
17. Are isolates recovered through the National Control Programs in auto-control checks included in the panel of isolates subjected to Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST)?
- Yes
 - No
 - Only in certain cases (specify):
18. What serotyping information is available for isolates collected through auto-control checks?
- Only target serovars are identified (SE= S. Enteritidis, ST= S. Typhimurium, SV= S. Virchow, SI= S. Infantis , SH= S. Hadar)
 - Other serovars (non- target) are also identified
19. Who stores the information generated through the auto-control checks? Is it possible to access the data?

Section 3. Official controls performed by Competent authority (CA)

20. What type of samples are collected for official controls in each of the production stages?

Hen categories (add others if appropriate)	Type of sampling
1/year adult hen (<1000 hen) from 24(+/-2) weeks	

1 flock /farm - end of the productive cycle 9 weeks before slaughterhouse	
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21. When are **official controls** typically conducted over the course of the year? (during one specific season, scattered through the year...)
22. Who perform the **official sampling**? Who pays? [e.g. authorised private vets perform the sampling and are paid by the regional veterinary services (state budget); sampling equipment is provided by the private laboratory testing the samples which includes the price in the invoice which is paid by the local state veterinary services (state budget)]
23. Who performs the laboratory test for the **official samples**? Who pays? [e.g. regional public laboratories perform the testing of official samples and costs related to this testing are entirely paid by the state budget]
24. What kind of laboratories are involved in **official controls**? (check all applicable)
- Official laboratory
 - Authorised laboratory
25. Are laboratory tests conducted according to specific protocols/methods? If so, please specify (e.g., ISO 6579, MicroSEQ, IQ- Check)
26. In case of positive flocks, in **official controls**, what measures are (typically) conducted?
27. Is there any compensation in case of measures after **official controls**? Who pays in case of compensation? [e.g. compensation is paid by the central level of the state veterinary services, or compensation is paid by an insurance fund fed by compulsory farmers contribution]
28. Are epidemiological surveys carried out when **auto-control checks** are conducted?
- Yes, always
 - Yes when/if positive results are obtained
 - No
 - Other (specify):
29. Are facilities inspected at the same time **official controls** are being conducted? Is there any information about the status of the buildings, the presence of biosecurity measures or the presence of rodents/other animals?
30. Is the size of the flock and poultry age recorded in in **official control** ?
- Yes
 - No
31. Are isolates recovered through the National Control Programs in **official controls** included in the panel of isolates subjected to Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST)?
- Yes
 - No

32. What serotyping information is available for isolates collected through official controls?

- Only target serovars are identified (SE= S. Enteritidis, ST= S. Typhimurium, SV= S. Virchow, SI= S. Infantis , SH= S. Hadar)
- Other serovars (non- target) are also identified

33. Who stores the information generated through the official controls? Is it possible to access the data?

Section 4. Biosecurity and other measures

34. Are biosecurity surveys conducted in the frame of the NCPs? (separated from autcontrol and official controls) If so, what is the frequency?

35. How is the cleaning, disinfection, disinsection and rooting (CCDR) process evaluated? Are there specific recommendation?

36. Is there any difference or specific recommendation for the CDDR in case of positive flocks?

37. Who implements this measure? Who provide the equipment/ service? Who pays?

38. Are there trained personnel for this CDDR?

39. What type of vaccines are approved for its use in this poultry category? Please provide commercial names of vaccines approved in your country

- Inactive
- Live

40. Is vaccination compulsory in the country? At what age are animals vaccinated? Is it allowed to vaccinate in laying phase?

41. How many weeks of life (hens) does these vaccines cover? Is all the cycle covered?

42. What is the information available about the vaccination coverage in the country (in laying hens)?

43. Who provides the vaccine and who performs the vaccination? Who pays the vaccine? Who pays the vaccinator? (e.g. farmers buy their vaccine to the private vets, send the paid invoices to the local state veterinary services which reimburse the farmers of the full amount and the vaccinator is paid by the regional state veterinary services)